

Epsilon-Logarithm Theorem

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Abstract. In this paper, we provide the Epsilon-Logarithm Theorem.

Theorem. Let $\mathbb{R}^+ = \{x | x \in \mathbb{R}, x > 0\}$. Let $k \in \mathbb{R}^+$. Then, there exists $x \in \mathbb{R}^+$ s.t.

$$\ln(x+k) - \ln(x) < \varepsilon \tag{1}$$

for $\forall \varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^+$.

Proof. If we simplify (1),

$$\ln(x+k) - \ln(x) = \ln\left(\frac{x+k}{x}\right) \tag{2}$$

$$= \ln\left(1 + \frac{k}{x}\right) < \varepsilon \tag{3}$$

Take the exponential function on both sides of (3),

$$1 + \frac{x}{k} < e^\varepsilon \tag{4}$$

Since $e^\varepsilon - 1 > 0$ ($\because \varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^+$), it is

$$\frac{k}{e^\varepsilon - 1} < x \tag{5}$$

Here, since $k \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $e^\varepsilon - 1 \in \mathbb{R}^+$ ($\because e^\varepsilon - 1 > 0$), so

$$\frac{k}{e^\varepsilon - 1} \in \mathbb{R}^+ \tag{6}$$

Therefore, there exists $x \in \mathbb{R}^+$ such that (5).

This completes the proof of the theorem. □